

COALESCE

Co-creating the EU Competence Centre for
Science Communication

Deliverable 2.2

Strategies to address critical challenges to effective science-society relations, including misinformation and trust

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Executive Summary

Overview of COALESCE and report objectives

About COALESCE

The [Coordinated Opportunities for Advanced Leadership and Engagement in Science Communication in Europe](#) (COALESCE)¹ project consolidates, further develops, and mainstreams generated knowledge and connections on science communication to build up the [European Competence Centre for Science Communication](#) virtual platform and its associated Academy. The development of a robust Competence Centre requires co-creation with multiple stakeholders, including researchers and practitioners, as active members of Communities of Practice. COALESCE contributes to this through instigating a network of National and Regional Hubs (N&R Hubs) and an interdisciplinary approach. It demonstrates the means for rapid mobilisation of science communication in times of crisis whilst navigating dis- and misinformation, and engendering trust in science. Supportive in this process is an accessible library of critical resources, toolkits, handbooks and training opportunities to research and innovation (R&I) actors across the European Research Area (ERA).

The COALESCE project ensures the effectiveness of and best practices for science communication through a concerted and focused effort made by an experienced, knowledgeable, and well-connected consortium. We build on and add to already existing forms of excellence in science communication, public engagement, and co-creation practices developed from the joint efforts of previous sister projects funded under the Horizon2020 SwafS-19 programme (Science with and for Society: ENJOI, PARCOS, NEWSERA, TRESKA, CONCISE, GlobalScape, RETHINK and QUEST). COALESCE continues and strengthens connections between academic researchers and practitioners representing the state of the art of science communication in Europe and defines and trains on best practices within Europe and beyond.

The consortium represents several unique selling points:

1. Integrating universities and higher education providers with SMEs;
2. Connecting participatory engagement methodologies and journalism practices with new channels for science communication;
3. Participating in agendas of national scientific bodies;

¹ DOI: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101095230>

4. Supported by existing science communication and journalism reference and university alliance networks.

Objectives

This deliverable focuses on strategies to address critical challenges to effective science–society relations, including misinformation and trust. In this deliverable, we provide an overview of approaches present in the field of science communication that nurture open and constructive science–society relationships. Specifically, we zoom in on approaches to navigate dis- and misinformation that support trust between science and society.

To this end, this report addresses three overall objectives:

1. Reporting on the state of art academic and practitioner insights on (navigating) dis- and misinformation, and maintaining trust in science.
2. Mapping science–society resources and tools (e.g. apps, widgets, guidelines, engagement formats) that support the navigation of dis- and misinformation and maintain trust in science.
3. Proposing sustainable strategies for navigating dis- and misinformation and maintaining trust that the European Competence Centre for Science Communication will build on.

Highlights

In light of the growing challenge of misinformation and the need to maintain public trust in science, science communication strategies must evolve to address both the dissemination of accurate information, as well as the complex social dynamics influencing public trust in science information. After comparing existing resources and tools, literature review and stakeholder feedback, we distinguish several types of approaches in the **field of science communication to navigate mis- and disinformation and to maintain public trust in science**. We note that science communication must encompass a complete spectrum of approaches: From one-way dissemination models that fact-check and debunk disseminated science information, to two-way, dialogical and participatory approaches, that comply with the often personal, social and contextual ways in which citizens make sense of science.

Key takeaways and insights

Several key approaches and strategies emerge from our analysis:

- **Empowering communicating scientists and science communicators:** Scientists and science communicators play a pivotal role in ensuring effective science–society relations and addressing challenges presented by misinformation. We showcase training materials that can support them in this endeavour.
- **Bridge between academic and public resources:** Approaches for effective science–society relations encompass bridging the gap between scholarly research and interventions that make academic studies more accessible. For example, simplified summaries and public–friendly publications, targeting multiple audiences, and guidelines for online best–practices.
- **From one-way dissemination and fact-checking approaches:** Traditional approaches to navigate misinformation and maintain public trust in science, such as fact-checking and debunking, remain critical practices. Assessing media content for credibility and producing high-quality, evidence-based counter-content are indispensable in correcting false claims and reinforcing public trust in science. Providing quality criteria for science communication practice and highlighting how science communication outputs should be produced to become (more) trustworthy in the perception of diverse audiences is key. Efforts should aim not only to correct misinformation but engage audiences in ways that resonate with their emotions, values, social context, and experiences.

- **... to two-way and multi-way engagement:** It is vital to engage citizens with science in ways that reflect their personal and contextual realities. Selected resources highlight the importance of dialogue, engagement, and participatory models to build effective and trustworthy science–society relations, allowing science communicators to connect with the diverse ways people interpret and interact with scientific knowledge. Their focus shifts from the knowledge gap or factual-based disagreements about scientific (mis)information to, approach misinformation challenges and ensure public trust in science from a social, relational perspective.
- **Addressing conflicting values, worldviews and emotions:** Effective science communication in light of a post-truth era, the challenges presented by misinformation and maintaining public trust in science, must also acknowledge and engage with the legitimacy of sometimes conflicting values, emotions, and social contexts of a diverse audience. By fostering conversations that address these factors, science communicators can create a more inclusive and trustworthy environment for discussing scientific issues. Developing a reflective practice for science communicators is essential in this.

1. Introduction

1.1 Science communication and the relationship between science and society

A good relationship between science and society is crucial for a healthy democracy and critical in addressing societal challenges and developing sustainable solutions to these challenges. The field of science communication plays an important role in the exchange of knowledge, perspectives and ideals between science and society, and therefore, the science–society relationship.

Maintaining a constructive relationship between science and society in light of socio–scientific issues is, however, not straightforward. Various scholars have described how misinformation undermines trust in democratic processes, scientific research and media – a subtle process that is exacerbated by (political) polarization, an increasingly digitised and fragmented science communication landscape and the ‘post-truth’ era (Choi et al., 2023; Hoes et al., 2024; Iyengar & Massey, 2019; Lewandowsky et al., 2023; Sardo et al., 2024). Furthermore, misinformation distorts our shared (public) understanding of scientific concepts, findings, and processes. It undermines trust in scientific institutions, disrupts informed decision–making, and can contribute to societal challenges like polarization and the erosion of trust in expertise and/or experts. Misinformation is often amplified by factors such as selective exposure, echo chambers, and the "post-truth" tendency to prioritize beliefs and emotions over empirical evidence (Iyengar et al., 2019; Vicario et al., 2016).

Although trust in scientific institutions remains relatively high overall, it fluctuates significantly on specific issues like climate change and biotechnology (Hendriks et al., 2016). Moreover, the rise of social media has made it easier for individuals to encounter misinformation and dismiss scientific evidence as "just another opinion". Against this backdrop, the field of science communication needs effective and collectively shared approaches to navigate misinformation and maintain trust in science.

1.2 Understanding dis- and misinformation

The terminology used to describe inaccurate information has been lacking in clarity due to inconsistencies in how a term such as misinformation has been applied (Scheufele & Krause, 2019). This led to approaches to develop consistency and nuance to the terminology describing false information (Amazeen et al., 2023). Typical of this are Wardle and Derakhshan’s (2017) three types of information disorder: disinformation – false information, deliberately created to cause harm; misinformation – information that is false but not created with the intention of causing harm; as well as mal–information – information

based on reality used to cause harm. Examples of dis- and/or misinformation include but are not limited to hoaxes, conspiracy theories and AI generated pictures that convey false information.

However, both in the common usage of the term and in research literature, misinformation is often applied in a broader sense to refer to inaccurate or misleading information that is shared – regardless of whether it is intentionally or accidentally false (Schmid-Petri & Bürger, 2021). Given the need to address the impacts of false information, regardless of intent, this broader definition is employed in this report.

More than one actor may be involved in the generation and spreading of false information. A content creator may disinform, and then re-posters or secondary spreaders of the disinformation engage in (unintentional) misinforming; all potentially reaching broad groups of people in society. Misinformation is commonly associated with online means of communication – and social media in particular. However, it also still occurs through more traditional means such as through word-of-mouth communication, self-published books or pamphlets.

In the context of communication about science-related information, misinformation presents a significant barrier to efforts to address climate change (Treen, Williams & O'Neill, 2020) and threatens public health (Swire-Thompson & Lazer, 2020). Misinformation is considered a crucial factor behind the decline in vaccination rates for conditions such as measles, mumps and rubella (Swire-Thompson & Lazer, 2020). In 2019, four European countries, Albania, the Czech Republic, Greece and the UK, lost their World Health Organisation (WHO) measles eradication status (BBC, 2019). A review of studies measuring the volume of misinformation about public health topics online found the prevalence of misinformation about specific topics to be 87% on individual social media platforms (Suarez-Lledo & Alvarez-Galvez, 2021). The challenge presented by misinformation is particularly acute at times of crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic due to the growth in its prevalence (European Parliament, 2023).

Scientific misinformation might be information, whether written, visual, auditory, or audiovisual, about (1) scientific research findings or processes, (2) technological developments or outcomes, or (3) their societal roles or impacts, that misleads recipients and intentionally causes harm, as judged by a broad group of stakeholders. Of course perspectives on what constitutes 'appropriate or accurate content', can vary over time and across cultural contexts. Thus, the identification of dis- and misinformation is culturally and temporally bound, and needs continuous evaluation and (re-)assessment.

1.2.1 Misinformation in a post-truth era

Different scholars have highlighted how the notion of 'post-truth' exacerbates the challenges posed by misinformation (Brüggemann, 2017; Harambam, 2021, Iyengar et al., 2019). The post-truth era is defined by a diminished reliance on objective, value-free facts, and an increased influence of emotions and personal beliefs in shaping public opinion and decision-making (Funtowicz et al., 1993). By prioritizing emotionally resonant narratives over empirical evidence, post-truth creates fertile ground for the spread of misinformation, reinforcing existing beliefs that deepen polarisation and societal divides (Harambam, 2021).

In the context of science communication, the post-truth context renders traditional models and strategies to deal with misinformation, such as the deficit model and fact-checking, insufficient – for example, they fail to address the emotional and ideological drivers that underpin the spread and uptake of misinformation (Harambam, 2020; Harambam, 2021). Instead, this context could or should call for development of participatory science communication approaches, that help foster dialogue, build trust, and engage audiences meaningfully (Leitch, 2021). The post-truth era thus serves as a critical backdrop that shapes how misinformation spreads and necessitates participatory, adaptive, and interdisciplinary strategies to address the impacts of misinformation effectively.

From the perspective of co-production of scientific knowledge, misinformation cannot be viewed merely as a failure of communication or dissemination of incorrect information. Instead, it should be understood within the broader context of the interaction between scientific, political, technological, and societal forces. Several articles suggest that the deficit model of communication, which assumes that providing more information will automatically correct misinformation, is inadequate in the current age (Choi et al., 2023, Grodzicka et al., 2021, Lewandowsky et al., 2017). Still, a substantial portion of the scientific community continues to hold on to the persistent but incorrect belief that public knowledge deficits are the primary cause of conflicts and controversies surrounding science (Nisbet & Scheufele, 2009).

In reality, personal situations, social context, underlying interests, moral values, and cultural beliefs play a far more significant role in shaping public perceptions of science, than scientific facts or misinformation (Rerimassie et al., 2021). Hence, there is a need for collaborative and participatory approaches where scientists, policymakers, and the public engage in co-producing knowledge. This requires acknowledging historical mistrust, especially in marginalized communities, and creating dialogue-based, context-sensitive

strategies that recognize the shared responsibility and focus on personal situations and social context of audiences, when addressing misinformation (Leitch, 2021).

In conclusion, addressing misinformation in science communication requires proactive strategies that foster trust, promote critical engagement, and adapt to the sociopolitical and technological contexts in which information is consumed. Such approaches consider moral values, ethical, social, cultural, political and economic factors in science communication approaches, next to a focus on dissemination or checking of the credibility and correctness of scientific facts.

1.3 The issue of trust in science–society relations

Trust in the context of science–society interactions is a multifaceted concept. It encompasses the degree by which society has confidence in scientists' competence, benevolence, and integrity to address socio–scientific issues (Chinn et al., 2022), and has a social, relational and emotional component that involves inter–dependency between science and society (Blobaum, 2016; Engdahl et al., 2014). With this, trust is seen as a dynamic feature of relationships that reduces complexity yet increases uncertainty in social interactions (Blobaum, 2016).

Science communication outputs often emphasize the 'trustworthiness' of science by presenting it as credible, new and robust scientific information – rather than providing a transparent or honest description of the origin, process of creation, and uncertainty of the presented scientific information to increase trustworthiness (Felt, 2018; Irwin, 2014). The field of science communication then easily becomes focused on whether the audience "gets" the scientific fact, rather than a deeper understanding of how these facts came to be and what uncertainties they contain. In relation to establishing trust between science and society, the field seems to privilege credibility of the presented information, rather than considering 'trust' as a dynamic relational concept. At the same time, science communication outputs are often expected and consulted to provide a univocal answer to inherently complex questions (Gross & McGoey, 2015).

Against this backdrop, uncertainty presents science communication with a difficult balancing act in light of establishing trust between science and society. When too much uncertainty is communicated, the presented scientific information might not seem credible, robust or 'trustworthy'. Yet, when too little uncertainty is communicated, there is a risk of overstating the potential benefits or over–simplification of the scientific information considering socio–scientific issues.

1.4 Implications for the field of science communication

Efforts to navigate misinformation and restore public trust often fail due to a lack of genuine dialogue and reflection on systems' and institutional level (Rathenau, 2018; Wynne, 2006). Several authors suggest a shift towards a co-productionist perspective for more socially responsive science communication in light of misinformation and trust (Hoes et al., 2024; Chilvers, 2020; Felt et al., 2018). For science communication to establish constructive science-society relationships, all involved actors should not only possess some basic scientific knowledge, but also be included in the conversation about the limits and biases of scientific knowledge and the generation of knowledge process and its uncertainties (Jasanoff, 2007). Furthermore, science communication approaches for effective science-society interactions should focus on personal, contextual situations by which citizens make sense of science, for example by participating actively in citizen science (Leguina et al., 2023) – next to a single focus on providing trustworthy scientific facts. This is also relevant as trust in science depends not only on the credibility of the scientist or institution and the education of the person trusting but also on their personal traits, past experiences, and values (University of Tartu, 2024).

Key recommendations include enhancing public engagement through deliberative forums and aligning science communication with audience values, transparently communicating scientific disagreements, and adopting a co-productive framework for public participation (Chinn et al., 2022; Chilvers, 2020; Bubela, 2009). Scientists are encouraged to disclose research uncertainties to build trust and strengthen the science-society relationship, to address political and ideological factors rather than refrain from them, and to engage citizens in decision-making processes (Chasemi et al., 2024; Hoes et al., 2024; Engdahl, 2014). Interventions against misinformation should preserve trustworthiness of reliable sources by focussing on trust as a central component in the dynamic way by which citizens make sense of (contested) scientific information, by addressing personal situations, values and emotions next to scientific facts in communication outputs (Hoes et al., 2024; Blobaum, 2016). Finally, scientists should maintain independence from external influences (Sardo et al., 2024). With this, we suggest a shift from the public deficit model to a two-way dialogue between science and the public, as this is needed to establish a constructive, trustworthy relationship between science and society.

2. Strategies for navigating and mitigating dis- and misinformation

In the previous section, we described the concept of science–society relations, focusing on misinformation and the issue of trust in the context of science communication. Numerous scholars have been working to address how to navigate dis- and misinformation while maintaining public trust in science. To contribute to this effort, we outline various topics in the state of the art literature below. We will focus on the current dominant science communication models: dissemination dialogue, participation and co-creation. Finally, we will highlight how these approaches deal with the implications of navigating misinformation and maintaining trust in the context of science communication – namely, the difficult balancing act of ensuring transparency and embracing uncertainty whilst accurately and clearly communicating scientific facts.

2.1 Science communication approaches: from debunking to engagement

The science communication field covers a wide spectrum of activities related to communication within science, technology and innovation. Both communicating topics related to science, technology and innovation to various societal audiences, as well as communication between scientists, technology developers and/or innovators and societal actors (stakeholders, citizens) are part of science communication. Therefore, science communication scholars and practitioners also speak of a spectrum of communication models, ranging from one-way communication models (including education and dissemination practices) to multi-way science communication (including dialogue, co-creation, engagement and participation practices) (Bucchi & Trench, 2021; Irwin, 2021; Trench, 2008).

Science Communication literature presents various interpretations of the models and assumptions underlying science communication (Davies & Horst, 2016; Trench, 2008). We identify three distinct models that emerged sequentially over time, each addressing the limitations of its predecessors in both theory and practice; one way dissemination, two-way dialogical and multi-way participatory approaches. Notably, these models developed in a cumulative manner, expanding the scope of approaches rather than replacing one another. Here, we describe these models to explore the diverse science communication approaches deployed to navigate misinformation and maintain public trust in science.

2.1.1 Misinformation and one-way dissemination science communication approaches

One-way science communication refers to a linear model of communication where scientific knowledge is transferred from experts (such as scientists or science communicators) to the public. In this model, there are no opportunities for interaction, dialogue, or feedback between the knowledge producers (scientists) and knowledge users (lay-audiences, stakeholders in wider society) (Turnhout et al., 2013). Historically, science communication primarily focused on disseminating knowledge from science to the public. In this model, science communicators play the role of gatekeepers of the quality of information that flows between science and society (Fahy & Nisbet, 2011). This includes science journalists, press office communicators, and staff at science centres and museums, who aim to inform the 'ordinary' citizen, spark interest in science, and promote public understanding of science.

These practices were largely shaped by the deficit model of science communication. The primary goal is to disseminate scientific facts, increase public understanding, and promote interest in science, often through mass media, lectures, press releases, or exhibitions. One-way science communication models focus on delivering accurate scientific information from experts to the public in a unidirectional manner. These models operate under the (false) assumption that lay audiences are vulnerable to misinformation due to a lack of understanding of credible scientific processes and/or knowledge deficits, for example because they lack access to correct facts or scientific education (Simis et al., 2016). In this approach there is a risk of assuming that providing accurate, evidence-based information will counter false claims and improve public understanding and acceptance of scientific information. Tools such as press releases, articles, social media posts, and public service announcements are also used to disseminate corrections. The goal here is to replace misinformation with accurate facts, clarify misunderstandings, and promote trust in scientific expertise.

However, while one-way models can efficiently distribute factual information, they have limitations. Research has shown that simply providing correct facts may not change attitudes or beliefs, especially when misinformation aligns with pre-existing values, identities, or emotions (Hoes et al., 2024). As it neglects engagement or dialogue, this model can overlook the complexities of how people process and respond to information, as well as prior relationships between individual communities and science. Such communication can fall into a 'one size fits all' approach, which instead can further damage these relationships (Dawson et al., 2024), often leading to resistance or further entrenchment of false beliefs. As a result, while fact-checking through one-way communication remains a valuable tool, it

is often more effective when combined with interactive, two-way approaches that address trust, values, and contextual understanding.

Recently, researchers have investigated the relationship between how one-way science communication approaches are deployed to fact-check the available scientific information in the public sphere (Fahy & Nisbet, 2011). Blanco-Alfonso et al. (2021) provide insights into the global strategies for combating misinformation through fact-checking. To elucidate the process of enhancing citizens' understanding of dubious messages, records from the fact-checking [Newtral](#) database, spanning the years 2018 and 2019, were analysed, exploring statistics and sources for both true and false content, as well as verification. The primary findings indicate that fraudulent messages outnumbered authentic ones, and that the media were the predominant source for disseminating verified dubious messages. Additionally, the findings reveal that governments were the main source of verification, credibility took precedence over immediacy in the fact-checking process, and politics was the most frequent topic of hoaxes. Their work, along with various studies during the COVID-19 pandemic, shows that while health-related misinformation was present, political misinformation predominated the infodemic landscape.

Harambam (2021; 2023) poses that the idea of 'fighting' or 'combatting' disinformation or misinformation for example by science communication aimed at 'debunking', and therein pretending that there is a wide consensus among researchers about the 'right scientific facts', can actually nurture or fuel scepticism (Harambam, 2021; 2023). He poses that science communication strategies therefore need to further develop in at least two aspects to restore trust between science and society:

- Putting efforts in communicating more richly, emphasising complexity and uncertainty, being more transparent about what is known and what not, and how (scientific) knowledge production is currently addressing these complexities and uncertainties.
- This is especially the case in times of increased polarisation: putting more effort in the facilitation of conversations between people with different perspectives regarding content that is to be considered dis- or misinformation. By facilitating conversations, concerns underlying various perspectives can be elicited and reflected upon. 'Supporters' of the dis- or misinformation can thereby be taken seriously, which is an important basis to rebuild trust in formal 'institutions' like government and science again. Through dialogue gathered perspectives can better science communication research and practice.

While one-way science communication, or dissemination, can be effective for spreading information quickly and broadly, it has been criticized for treating the public as passive recipients of knowledge and for overlooking the public's existing expertise, values, and

ability to engage with science critically. It is often seen as non-inclusive and failing to account for the complex ways people interpret and integrate scientific information within their social, cultural, and personal contexts.

For example, before the COVID-19 pandemic, research carried out by Scheufele and Krause (2019) highlights the complex nature of misinformation in the United States, particularly concerning science topics. Their work emphasises the need for a systems-based approach to mitigate the effects of misinformation, incorporating individual, group, and societal factors. The authors provide an extensive analysis of the increasing concerns regarding public misinformation in the United States, with a particular focus on science issues. They underscore the necessity of empirical research in developing effective science communication strategies to mitigate the impact of misinformation in the public sphere. Here it becomes clear that two-way and multi-way approaches to science communication are needed to consider the contextual and complex nature of science-society relations.

2.1.2 Misinformation and two-way, dialogical communication approaches

Dialogue models adopt a more contextual perspective on the relationship between science and society, recognizing the validity of diverse sources of knowledge and ways of understanding, as well as the integral role of values and ideals in addressing complex societal issues. This shift coincided with broader calls for greater public participation and influence in decision-making, driven in part by declining trust in science and institutions, such as governments, in some societies (Wynne, 2006). The focus moved away from merely improving public understanding of science toward actively engaging the public and creating deliberative spaces where various stakeholders could exchange perspectives and make value estimations in relation to science.

As such, two-way communication models in science communication emphasise dialogue, interaction, and mutual exchange between scientific knowledge producers (e.g. researchers), the conveyors of scientific information (e.g. science communicators), and the public. These models represent a shift away from the traditional and linear one-way model of communication – recognizing that effective communication involves not just disseminating or checking facts, but engaging with public knowledge, values, and perspectives.

In relation to navigating misinformation, two-way communication approaches are particularly valuable because they foster trust through building relationships and creating opportunities for meaningful discussion. Disinformation and misinformation, which the science communication field may be tasked with addressing, are often deeply intertwined with seemingly unrelated topics, such as politics or the influence of enterprises and institutions (Harambam, 2019; 2023). They capture interest of recipients by 1) calling on

their fears for loss in their own wellbeing or that of their loved ones, and often by 2) filling gaps in formally developed information sources.

Therefore, scholars have proposed that to counter dis- and misinformation, science communication approaches should not only focus on filling ‘the knowledge gap’, but rather engaging audiences in conversations that acknowledge their concerns, beliefs, and lived experiences (Elliot et al., 2024). This engagement can help connect scientific knowledge and public understanding, addressing the emotional, cultural, and social dimensions that often fuel the spread of misinformation. For example, platforms like public forums, citizen science initiatives, and participatory workshops, allow scientists and the public to clarify misconceptions, and explore contentious issues collaboratively. By fostering dialogue, two-way models not only provide factual corrections but also empower individuals to critically evaluate information, ask questions, and become active participants in science-related discussions.

2.1.3 Misinformation and multi-way, participatory communication approaches

The dialogue model has faced its own criticisms, such as insufficient opportunities for non-experts and lay audiences to participate in decision-making processes. Additionally, scholars have argued that deficit thinking often persists in dialogue-focused science communication models, be it in rebranded forms (Gregory & Lock, 2008; Wynne, 2006). For example, dialogue is often used as a way to still convince lay audiences of certain scientific information – therewith focusing on scientific facts instead of the legitimate concerns that audiences might have. Hence, the shift towards dialogue models emerged alongside a broader call for public influence and participation in scientific knowledge creation and decision-making processes.

The participatory, co-creative science communication model emphasises the involvement of diverse stakeholder groups and publics at various stages of the research and innovation process, aiming to enhance public influence and strengthen connections to policy-making and action (Irwin, 2008; Stilgoe et al., 2014; Wilsdon & Willis, 2004). The participation model of science communication seeks to reflect the full complexity of science-society issues, including scientific uncertainty, (tacit) gaps in knowledge, the coexistence of multiple legitimate knowledge sources and perspectives, and the social shaping of science and technology.

In participation models, communication is viewed as a co-creative process of interpreting and integrating different perspectives. It begins with recognizing the complex realities of societal problems and the diverse range of actors whose varying viewpoints lead to different, and often contested, definitions of those problems. A key component of this model is the co-production of knowledge through facilitation of exchange between

scientific and nonscientific actors. The field of science communication provides an interface where these different actors can interact and thereby enhances the public's influence on policy agenda setting, and policy decision-making (Wilsdon & Willis, 2004; Giardullo, 2023).

Participation models in science communication, particularly through co-creative approaches, provide a collaborative framework for navigating misinformation by emphasizing shared knowledge production and active engagement of diverse stakeholders. Unlike traditional one-way or deficit models, participation models acknowledge that addressing misinformation requires more than simply transmitting scientific facts. One example could be found in the NEWSERA EU-funded project, where citizen science and the role of citizen scientists was explored to counteract misinformation (Leguina, 2023), as these can become science communicators and micro-influencers on their own local environments.

By engaging the public, policymakers, and other stakeholders as partners in knowledge creation, these models promote a deeper understanding of societal concerns, local knowledge, and lived experiences that often intersect with scientific issues. This collaborative process allows the field of science communication to identify and clarify misconceptions, while addressing the root causes of misinformation –such as distrust, scientific uncertainty, or competing perspectives –through transparent, reciprocal and inclusive communication (Canfield & Menezes, 2020).

The COALESCE project, while placing co-creation at its core, will make use of all approaches mentioned above – in line with the plea of Scheufele and Krause (2019), and informed by the ideas of Harambam (2021, 2023) – aiming to curate sustainable strategies for navigating dis- and misinformation within a dedicated section under the virtual platform of the European Competence Centre for Science Communication.

2.2 Building transparency and addressing uncertainty

Science communication and trust in science are intertwined. While trust in science can be a factor affecting the success of communication, science communication can in turn promote or affect trust in science ([IANUS Project](#), 2023). It is also essential to differentiate between warranted and unwarranted trust (University of Tartu, 2024). Blind trust in science can even lead to an increased susceptibility to pseudoscience when false claims are framed with scientific references. Efforts to combat misinformation must balance fostering trust with promoting critical evaluation to mitigate misplaced confidence in pseudoscientific narratives (O'Brien et al., 2021).

Although the majority of the public has a positive image of scientists, especially with regard to their ability, fewer trust the honesty and integrity of scientists, or that they act in the public interest (Pew Research, 2024; Cologna, V. et al. 2024; Wissenschaft im Dialog, 2022; FECYT, 2022; European Commission, 2021). While malpractice in research represents a significant threat to the public's trust in science, so too does the manner in which science is communicated to the public, particularly in the context of socially controversial or political topics.

Poor quality science communication, a lack of transparency, an exaggeration of results, or a lack of information about the uncertainty and tentativeness of scientific results can damage trust (Morgan, 2024; Intemann, 2023), especially in times of crisis (DeLong et al., 2024). Even well-intentioned communication from the media or from within the scientific community itself can contribute to the proliferation of noise and misinformation (Intemann, 2023; Fisher, 2022; West & Bergstrom, 2021; Vera et al., 2022). A review of previous projects (Antoniou & Antoniou, 2024) highlights various obstacles they faced while attempting to foster public trust in science, whether explicitly or indirectly. These difficulties relate to the diversity of public engagement, the (un)availability of science representatives, the public's availability and motivation, and the quality of scientific methods and results.

A considerable number of science and health news stories are disseminated to the general public with exaggerations that are misleading and inaccurate. Examples include inferences of causality derived from observational studies, expectations of treatment outcomes based on mouse trials, and recommendations for patients without sufficient supporting evidence. Such misrepresentations can influence the interpretation of results and generate false expectations among the public (Boutron et al., 2019). Although the media has traditionally been held responsible for this distortion of scientific results, it is possible that various actors may be contributing to this game of broken telephone. Consequently, there is an increasing body of evidence indicating that the source of these distortions may be found in press releases, in scientific articles themselves, or even, at an earlier stage, in grant applications and funding calls (Summer et al., 2014; Triunfol & Gouveia, 2021; Millar et al., 2022a; 2022b; 2023).

Similarly, a reduction in independent science journalism, coupled with the pursuit of attention and media targeting research personnel, academic institutions, research organisations and science publishers, may result in a biased representation of science in the media (FECYT, 2024; Entradas et al. 2020; Franks et al., 2022; Weingart, 2017, 2019) and detract from its integrity and credibility (Franks et al., 2022). This is particularly pertinent in the context of social media, where the pursuit of attention and the deployment of strategies such as polarisation, favoured by algorithms, can result in scientists and institutions contributing to the proliferation of misinformation and noise in the informational

landscape (Jucá et al., 2024; Schäfer, 2024). The brevity and interactive nature of social media present unique challenges for science communication. These platforms can encourage researchers to exaggerate their findings, defend positions more vehemently than they would in offline communication, and engage in debates that extend beyond their areas of expertise (Morgan, 2024).

Uncertainty is an intrinsic aspect of scientific inquiry. Nevertheless, conveying uncertainty is a challenging endeavor, and scientists and communicators are frequently concerned that doing so may confuse the public, elicit criticism, indicate incompetence, or even erode confidence in science (Kupper, 2020). Furthermore, there is concern that openly communicating uncertainty may be exploited by self-interested actors to undermine the credibility of science and mislead the public, such as corporations with economic interests (Oreskes & Conway, 2010). During the uncertainty of the COVID-19 pandemic, misinformation messages addressed the unanswered questions posed by governments, health authorities, and the scientific community regarding the novel coronavirus. Notably, two distinct phases of COVID-19 rumour circulation were identified. The first phase spanned from the WHO's pandemic declaration in March 2020 until late November, before mass vaccinations began. Initially, rumours did not reference vaccines. The spread of rumours in this initial phase decreased as the epidemic peaked, consistent with Eysenbach's (2002) earlier predictions about infodemics. As the peak of infections rose significantly, the dissemination of rumours diminished (Moreno-Castro, 2022).

Nevertheless, there is growing evidence that communicating uncertainty in an appropriate manner not only has no adverse effects but can also safeguard against a loss of confidence when evidence undergoes changes (Gustafson & Rice, 2020; Kreps & Kriner, 2020b; Dries et al., 2024). Studies have shown that transparent messages are perceived as equally or more trustworthy than persuasive ones, particularly by skeptical audiences (Kerr et al., 2022). Transparency not only clarifies the iterative nature of scientific discovery but also reduces the risk of exaggerated claims that can mislead the public (Adams et al., 2019). For instance, clinicians communicating the limitations and uncertainties of COVID-19 tests have been shown to foster informed decision-making and avoid misinterpretation (Watson et al., 2020). Research has also shown that disclosing uncertainties—whether numerical, verbal, or contextual—can enhance perceptions of honesty and credibility, especially when communicated by the original researchers (Ratcliff & Wicke, 2022). However, how we communicate uncertainty matters.

If we consider wording, research indicates that using hedges (e.g., "might" or "possibly") enhances credibility, while conflict-based uncertainty (e.g., disagreements between scientists) can undermine trust (Howell, 2020). How media portrayals of science influence public perceptions should also be considered. Research has shown that while 'crisis'

narratives (emphasizing failures, conflicts, fraud, misconduct, or errors) can erode trust and belief in science, 'problem explored' narratives (presenting scientific challenges or issues as part of an ongoing process of inquiry and improvement) mitigate negative effects and enhance trust. For communicators and journalists, emphasizing science's self-correcting nature is key to maintaining credibility and fostering public trust (Ophir & Jamieson, 2021).

Communicating scientific uncertainty is also recommended in long-term communication actions. For example, museums and educational institutions have successfully integrated uncertainty into their exhibits, demonstrating that audiences can appreciate and even support such transparency without losing trust in science (Altenmüller et al., 2024). Strategies include presenting uncertainty as an integral aspect of science, contextualizing it within real-world applications and addressing potential misconceptions. This approach aims to create more informed, engaged audiences without undermining confidence in scientific institutions (Kupper, 2020).

In order to address challenges such as misinformation or potential loss of trust, it is essential to empower audiences to discern credible information and counter the appeal of pseudoscientific narratives. This can be achieved by prioritising responsible, evidence-informed science communication, promoting transparency, sharing data, explicitly communicating uncertainty and conflicts of interest, and reporting not only results, but also processes. This should include information about the ways in which that knowledge was produced and why those methods are reliable (Nisbet & Scheufele, 2009; Weingart & Guenther, 2016; Howell, 2020; O'Brien et al., 2021). It is also recommended to avoid oversimplified or alarmist messaging (Intemann, 2023).

Given these challenges and opportunities, the Competence Centre plays a vital role in equipping communicators, journalists, and researchers with the tools and training needed for effective, evidence-based science communication. Through its virtual platform and network of N&R Hubs, we will foster the development of resources and training modules focused on transparency, communicating uncertainty, and addressing misinformation. By promoting responsible science communication, the Competence Centre supports trust-building efforts and empowers stakeholders to navigate the complexities of science-society relations, ensuring communication practices align with the highest standards of integrity and public engagement.

3. Mapping and utilizing existing resources

3.1 Mapping existing tools, resources, and reports

Researchers working in numerous international projects are dedicated to analysing the spread and impact of dis- and misinformation globally. Traditionally, these studies are published in academic journals or detailed reports that, while insightful, are often confined to scholarly circles, fact-checking platforms, and international observatories (GDI², 2018; EDMO³, 2018; and OCDE⁴, 2022; among others⁵). Fortunately, many reports are accessible.

There are also institutions world-wide, that work on disinformation, who provide limited access to their reports and tools. As a consequence, only specific audiences such as researchers or analysts are making use of them. For example, at Indiana University, The Observatory on Social Media⁵ (OSoMe, pronounced awesome) is a joint project of the Centre for Complex Networks and Systems Research (CNetS) at the Luddy School and the Media School. OSoMe unites data scientists and journalists in studying the role of media and technology in society and building tools to analyse and counter disinformation and manipulation on social media. Also, some reports and tools on [UNESCO's website](#) are also only accessible when they are purchased.

However, the global adoption of open science practices is changing this scenario, and organisations such as the European Commission and the [Joint Research Centre](#) (JRC) pay significant importance to open access to reports and recommendations related to this topic, such as those that can be found at the [JRC repository](#). Their latest publication “Trustworthy Public Communication” is especially relevant here, as it focuses on how communicators can strengthen the future of democracies. Although mis- and disinformation strategies are not central to this work, it does address them in the context of the fundamentals of establishing trust in public administrations, primarily through trustworthy behaviour (Smillie & Scharfbillig, 2024).

²Global Disinformation Index (GDI) was established in 2018 as a not-for-profit entity built on the three pillars of neutrality, independence, and transparency. It is available a lot of reports about disinformation around the world: <https://www.disinformationindex.org/>

³The European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO) is dedicated to combating online disinformation. By uniting fact-checkers, media literacy experts, and academic researchers, EDMO fosters a comprehensive approach to understanding and analysing disinformation. EDMO is supported by an expansive network of 14 national or multinational hubs that operate across 28 countries in the EU and EEA. These hubs are strategically positioned to identify and address the unique challenges and vulnerabilities of the digital media landscape within their respective regions and tailor strategies that mitigate the spread and impact of disinformation in diverse socio-political contexts. The reports are available via: <https://edmo.eu/about-us/edmoeu/>

⁴OECD (2022). Misinformation and disinformation: An international effort using behavioural science to tackle the spread of misinformation, *OECD Public Governance Policy Papers*, No. 21, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/b7709d4f-en>

⁵Access to the different tools and reports of OSoMe via: <https://osome.iu.edu/tools?>

Moreover, several ongoing European-funded projects have been highlighted by the [European Research Executive Agency](#) (REA) for their contributions in mitigating disinformation campaigns; the development of platforms that address disinformation challenges on social media and that facilitate investigations, and leveraging a decentralised, transparent, and community-driven approach to combat echo chambers created by AI-curated feeds on social media.

In terms of work done, REA's study has identified social media as a key driver of misinformation and disinformation, amplified by algorithms favoring engagement over accuracy. Studies highlight how echo chambers and psychological factors like confirmation bias and the Dunning-Kruger effect⁶ make certain groups more prone to spreading false information.

However, the perspectives of scholarly research on dis- and misinformation are different from those in the general public. This perspective variety underscores the need for innovative approaches to better (re-)connect rigorous academic study and the public sphere. COALESCE proposes a novel approach to this challenge by drafting different strategies to address critical challenges to effective science-society relations, including misinformation. In this deliverable, we collect previous work done in SwafS-19 projects and others, and a spectrum of resources that could potentially become available on the Competence Centre following a set of [standards, principles and criteria \(SPCs\)](#) and thereby curate strategies in regards of multiple stakeholders, based on the previous experiences fostered by the European Commission, such as the European Digital Media Observatory actions.

Since 2018, the [EDMO](#), funded by the European Commission, is mapping the media literacy landscape across Europe through its comprehensive project, [Mapping the Media Literacy Sector](#). This initiative aims to create detailed profiles for each member state, providing a deep understanding of media literacy activities and frameworks related to disinformation. These profiles collectively offer an overview of national policies, key stakeholders, the status of media literacy in national curricula, and activities beyond formal education. This resource fosters collaboration and knowledge sharing among European countries, enhancing collective efforts to combat disinformation and promote media literacy. Each country's profile is a resource for comprehending that particular nation's specific media literacy environment. For instance, currently, the profiles for 9 countries, including Ireland, Italy, and Luxembourg, are accessible online:

⁶The Dunning-Kruger effect describes how people with low expertise often overestimate their competence, while highly skilled individuals may underestimate theirs. This phenomenon was first identified by David Dunning and Justin Kruger in 1999 (Dunning et al., 2003).

- [Ireland](#) – offers a thorough exploration of its media literacy policies, educational integration, critical organisations involved, and notable initiatives to combat disinformation.
- [Italy](#) – provides comprehensive information on the country's strategic approaches to media literacy, significant stakeholders, and the integration of media literacy within the educational system and broader societal context.
- [Luxembourg](#) – highlights national strategies, educational frameworks, and critical actors dedicated to enhancing media literacy and addressing misinformation.

Several European countries are developing national-level data sharing (EDMO hubs) and simultaneously uploading the information to EDMO, including [information on media literacy](#). The observatory continuously updates these profiles with new member states, adding on an ongoing basis information about stakeholders and fresh projects and activities. The objective is to constantly update the work carried out in media literacy across Europe so that the profiles continue as far and complete as possible. These resources have value for other organisations because they are a centralised and visible repository of media literacy information on disinformation. These resources are handy to support policymakers, educators, researchers, and practitioners in the critical aspects of their work by facilitating informed decision-making and helping develop concrete initiatives focusing on media literacy adapted to each Member State. Civil organisations and institutions' engagement in this initiative is essential to its success because of the community.

3.1.1 Sources from SwafS-19 projects for navigating science-related misinformation

We mined a database created specifically under COALESCE that gathers all results and resources derived directly from the EU-funded SwafS-19 projects (ENJOI, PARCOS, NEWSERA, TRESKA, CONCISE, GlobalScape, RETHINK and QUEST) with the initial label 'misinformation' and after reading provided description and abstract for keywords (eg. misinformation, disinformation, fake news, trust and others). This means that the topic of misinformation was either discussed or implied in some way. This may not be an extensive list.

Table 1. Reports and resources of SwafS-19 projects relevant to the challenge of misinformation

Name of resource // project	Strategy / approach	Topics Covered	Who may profit from this resource	Link
D5.3 Guide of Science Communication in Citizen Science Projects and Citizen Science Journalism: "Tackling Misinformation: How to Deliver Ethically Sound and Reliable Initiatives" (p. 12-15) <i>// NEWSERA PROJECT</i>	Multi-way (co-creation)	Good and bad practices, and recommendations to avoid dis- and misinformation when communicating about projects.	Science communicators, researchers and citizens involved in (citizen) science projects	https://zenodo.org/record/7752525
12 Quality Indicators for Science Communication: Guide for Science Communicators <i>// QUEST PROJECT</i>	one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Trustworthiness and Scientific Rigour; Presentation and Style; Connection with Society.	Science communicators	https://questproject.eu/wp2-measuring-and-assessing-science-communication-quality/
Webinar – Quality Science Communication in a Digital World <i>// RETHINK PROJECT</i>	One-way (dissemination), Two-way (dialogue)	What is quality scicomm in different contexts; quality criteria to assess quality scicomm; sensemaking.	Science communicators	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Tcm8jPTLR4E&t=89s
Webinar – Making sense of (mis)information in a digital world <i>// RETHINK PROJECT</i>	Two-way (dialogue), Multi-way (co-creation)	Understanding misinformation in a post-truth era; sensemaking.	Science communicators, researchers	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3wCn5bvXHds&t=12s
12 Quality criteria for online science communication <i>// RETHINK PROJECT</i> D3.2 – Report on experts' views on current science communication quality and demands Infographic Explainer video	One-way (dissemination), Two-way (dialogue)	Quality criteria for online science communication; Quality framework	Science communicators	https://zenodo.org/record/4061349#X3WUjmgzZPY & https://zenodo.org/records/6576619/files/RETHINK_Capsules_WP3.pdf?download=1 &

				https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SMrOofK-UQo
<p>Making sense of the COVID-19 pandemic: citizen sensemaking practices and the implications for science communication // RETHINK PROJECT</p> <p>How citizens make sense of uncertain, ambiguous science during crisis – explainer video</p> <p>D2.2 Making sense of the COVID-19 pandemic: An analysis of the dynamics of citizen sensemaking practices across Europe</p> <p>D2.3 Report on the barriers and opportunities for opening-up citizens’ sensemaking practices through science communication</p>	<p>Two-way (dialogue)</p> <p>Multi-way (co-creation)</p>	<p>How citizens make sense of uncertain, ambiguous scientific information during crisis & implications for practice of science communication.</p> <p>Who and what were trusted and why.</p>	<p>Science communicators, researchers, general audience</p>	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IzIBvNUcCH4</p> <p>&</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/records/4507041</p> <p>&</p> <p>https://www.rethinkscicomm.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/D2.3-RETHINK_Derivable.pdf</p>
<p>Best practices for science communication – Six virtues for the reflective science communication practitioner // RETHINK PROJECT</p> <p>D2.5 Best practices for science communication in post-truth era</p> <p>Towards the reflective science communication practitioner – Academic paper</p> <p>Infographic – Best practices for science communication in post truth era</p>	<p>Two-way (dialogue),</p> <p>Multi-way (co-creation)</p>	<p>Best practices for scicomm practitioners and communicating researchers in a digital, post-truth era; focus on reflective practice.</p>	<p>Science communicators, researchers</p>	<p>https://www.rethinkscicomm.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/RETHINK_D2.5_Best-practice-for-science-communication.pdf</p> <p>&</p> <p>https://jcom.sissa.it/article/pubid/JCOM_2104_2022_A02/</p> <p>&</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/records/6594319/files/RETHINK_Capsules_WP2.pdf?download=1</p>
<p>Policy brief: Science Communication in support of</p>	<p>Applicable on one-way,</p>	<p>Practical advice and tools for better</p>	<p>Science-policy</p>	<p>https://trescaproject.eu/wp-content/</p>

evidence-based policymaking // TRESCA PROJECT	two-way and multi-way approaches	researcher-policymaker engagement, aimed at nurturing mutual understanding and trust. Includes a MOOC, a video by Kurzgesagt and a widget	brokers	uploads/2022/03/D6.6-FINAL-TRESCA-Policy-Brief-including-disclaimer.pdf%22
White paper on best practices for producing science communication videos // TRESCA PROJECT	One-way (dissemination)	Six best practice recommendations for trustworthy and reliable online science videos.	Content developers	https://trespaproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/TRESCA_D4.2_White-paper-on-best-practices-for-SciCom-videos.pdf
Science Communication: Communicating Trustworthy Information in the Digital World // TRESCA PROJECT	One-way	Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) for scientists, journalists and policy makers to learn how to best facilitate reliable and trustworthy science communication	Scientists, journalists, policy makers	https://www.coursera.org/learn/communicating-trustworthy-information-in-the-digital-world
Prototype of a misinformation widget working on encrypted communication channels to help identify trustworthy sources // TRESCA PROJECT	Applicable on one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Proof of Concept (PoC) development of a Misinformation Widget MsW which would run through encrypted communication channels like WhatsApp	Communication technology developers	https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5eed23f80&appId=PPGMS
Science Communication on Social Media: Good Practices // QUEST PROJECT	Emphasis on Trust, applicable on one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Guidelines for three scicomm quality pillars (trustworthiness and scientific rigour, presentation and style, and societal connection) translated for social media context	Science communication professionals aiming to improve their social media presence	https://trespaproject.eu/download/science-communication-on-social-media-good-practices/

QUEST Toolkits for quality science communication // QUEST PROJECT	Emphasis on Trust, applicable on one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Co-designed guides, checklists, presentations, and other tools to improve clarity, engagement, and trust in science communication across various platforms and settings	Scientists, journalists, museum facilitators, and social media managers	https://questproject.eu/toolkits/
ENJOI SPIs (standards, principles and indicators) for Open Science Communication // ENJOI PROJECT	Emphasis on Trust, applicable on one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Promoting transparency, accuracy, and inclusivity through integrity, rigorous methodology, relevance to the audience, genuine engagement, and the inclusion of diverse perspectives	Journalists and content producers	https://enjoiscicomm.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/ENJOI_Standard_Principles_Indicators.pdf
ENJOI Focus report on solution journalism; interactive graphic tool in section 7 // ENJOI PROJECT	One-way approach	Constructive or solution journalism (identifying problems and presenting actionable solutions), definition, analysis and case studies	Policymakers and journalists	https://zenodo.org/record/7472887 or https://public.flourish.studio/visualisation/11166749/?utm_source=showcase&utm_campaign=visualisation/11166749
ENJOI Analysis report on the use of data and open science results // ENJOI PROJECT	One-way approach	Science journalism media landscape explored through the prism of engagement, data, general innovation, and solutions	Science journalists	https://zenodo.org/record/7472875
Citizen Science as a communication tool in the Post-Factual Era (D3.7) // NEWSERA PROJECT	Multi-way approach	On the potential of citizens involved in Citizen Science to contribute	Journalists, researchers, and other Actors interested and/or	https://zenodo.org/record/7689045#.ZABrBnbMIUF

Check case-study methodology (page 24) and checklist (page 41)		significantly to scientific knowledge producers and educators, to eventually contribute to navigating misinformation	involved in citizen science but could also be applied to other scientific projects	
Co-identifying ethics and misinformation issues in CS using a case study model // NEWSERA PROJECT	Multi-way approach	Two workshop formats to analyse how citizen science can contribute to navigating misinformation	Researchers, citizens, science communication professionals, policymakers, journalists and other actors interested and/or involved in citizen science and scientific projects that may elicit ethical dilemmas	https://zenodo.org/record/7689045/#.ZABrBnbMIUF (pg. 24)
DATA4CitSciNews – Data Journalism, Misinformation and Citizen Science Event // NEWSERA & ENJOI PROJECTS	Applicable on one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Lecture: <i>Misinformation / Fake News – what’s new?</i> , “FARE – Fake News Recommendations –” and “FARE_AUDIT an Auditing System of Differential Tracking and Search Engine Results (FARE_AUDIT) – Fake News and Real People”	Journalists, designers, researchers, citizens, science communication professionals	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EWdDfJ7yFoY&t=4947s – at 1:01:53

As can be seen in this overview, the majority of the SwafS-19 resources suggest navigating dis- and misinformation for researchers, journalists, science communicators and citizens through opening up of the scientific research process (e.g. through citizen science and co-creation), and, mostly, improving informative communication (aiming for effective, high-quality (counter) content development). These are effective strategies to navigate some forms of disinformation and misinformation among the general public, especially

when it is needed to quickly reach large groups of people, as those experienced in times of crisis. The downside is that these strategies for good quality science communication may also be applied by those intended to generate disinformation. Furthermore, while current resources do emphasise the importance of science–society relationship building (including citizen science), strategies concerning stakeholder and citizen engagement, dialogue and participation for the context of navigating dis- or misinformation seem to remain underexplored.

Table 2 lists resources produced by and gathered during COALESCE stakeholder engagement activities. These include suggestions by participants during [co-design sessions](#) (Magalhães et al., 2024), interviews, and online surveys. This overview attempts by no means to be complete, as it reflects current information available and should be considered open to expansion.

In fact, while researching [CORDIS](#), we found that since 2014, under the Horizon 2020 program, the EU's R&I initiatives have funded 140 projects related to misinformation through Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe programs. However, these projects have not specifically focused on scientific misinformation. Most projects address misinformation and its societal impacts, mostly political, but sometimes also scientific, and vaccine–related issues, with a particular emphasis on this after the COVID–19 outbreak in 2019–2020. Key focus areas include social media misinformation and political misinformation. Many of these projects adopt interdisciplinary approaches, combining behavioral science, artificial intelligence, social science, and media studies. They aim to tackle challenges in democratic societies, assess policy impacts, and facilitate cross–national comparisons. Additionally, some projects prioritize training stakeholders, such as journalists, healthcare professionals, and policymakers, to enhance their resilience to misinformation. A total of 56 deliverables are available on the same database related to misinformation, with some focusing on scientific misinformation, primarily those produced by SwafS–19–funded projects that are included in Table 1.

Examples of other relevant, non–SwafS–19–related, science communication or misinformation–adjacent projects include:

- [JITSUVAX](#): Focuses on vaccine misinformation by training healthcare professionals using refutational learning techniques.
- [COVINFORM](#): Developed an online portal and visual toolkit for stakeholders in government, public health, and civil society to analyze and understand COVID–19 responses.
- [POLARCLIMATE](#): Aims to combat climate scepticism and societal polarization that hinder effective climate action through interdisciplinary methods combining data science and climate communication.

- [SOMA](#) (Social Observatory for Disinformation and Social Media Analysis): Analyzes social media dynamics and their relationship with other sectors to address risks posed by the spread of fake news and misleading information.
- [FARE AUDIT](#): This project aims to increase transparency and reduce disinformation by developing a tool to audit online search engines. The findings will reveal how browsing behavior impacts search results and the chances of encountering disinformation. First results have been submitted.

Some of these projects are still ongoing, and COALESCE will strive to establish close connections with them to incorporate their findings into the science misinformation toolkit that will be launched in the CC. Another project of interest is [AI4TRUST](#), which aims to combat disinformation on social media by developing a hybrid system that combines AI and human expertise.

Table 2. Resources gathered or co-created under COALESCE relevant to science misinformation

NAME OF RESOURCE // PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Informando de ciencia con ciencia (Reporting Science Scientifically) - in Spanish // Fundación Lilly	Applicable on one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Best practices in science journalism	Science communication professionals	https://www.fecyt.es/es/system/files/publications/attachments/2023/05/informando_de_ciencia_con_ciencia_fundacionlilly_0.pdf
<p>The current era places an unprecedented social responsibility on science journalism. Science is no longer the exclusive domain of experts; rapid scientific advancements and their direct impact on our lives have significantly heightened public interest, especially during the pandemic. This surge in interest has led to greater prominence of science in the media, coinciding with challenges such as information overload, fake news, and conspiracy theories propagated effectively through social media. This volume explores the methods and peculiarities of science journalism, featuring contributions from scicomm researchers and professional science journalists, presenting a practical and uniform approach. Each chapter begins with a theoretical overview, followed by practical recommendations and case studies, concluding with key messages and a curated bibliography.</p>				
NAME OF RESOURCE // PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Policies to tackle disinformation in EU member states – part 1 // EDMO	Applicable on one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Disinformation, policy	Science communication professionals	https://edmo.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/Policies-to-tackle-disinformation-in-EU-member-states-during-elections-Report.pdf
<p>This report examines the impact of disinformation particularly during elections and policy responses to address it, thus not necessarily science disinformation. Using insights from the Media Pluralism Monitor (MPM), it reviews EU-wide approaches and measures in seven member states, highlighting non-legislative strategies and controversial legal actions. It also assesses their alignment with European frameworks and implications for free expression.</p>				

NAME OF RESOURCE // PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Policies to tackle disinformation in EU member states – part 2 // EDMO	Applicable on one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Disinformation, policy	Science communication professionals	https://edmo.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Policies-to-tackle-disinformation-in-EU-member-states---Part-II.pdf
<p>This second part of the report continues addressing the growing problem of disinformation. It examines the European Union's approach and explores policy examples from nine EU member states and four non-EU Balkan countries. While non-legislative methods are common, some countries have adopted legal measures, which remain controversial due to potential impacts on freedom of expression. The paper also questions whether national policies effectively complement a Europe-wide strategy against disinformation.</p>				
NAME OF RESOURCE // PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Crisis Navigator for Rapid Mobilisation of Science Communication // COALESCE	Applicable on one-way approaches	Crisis communication, misinformation	Science communication professionals	https://zenodo.org/records/11446975
<p>The Crisis Navigator is designed as a strategic resource to support the rapid mobilisation of science communication in times of crisis. The first version specifically addresses science communicators, based on the guiding question: How can science communicators contribute when a crisis emerges?</p>				
NAME OF RESOURCE // PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Policy Brief on excellent scicomm for society at large through informal activities // COALESCE	Applicable on one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Trust	Decision-makers, science communication professionals	https://zenodo.org/records/11082053
<p>This report examines how science communication can address complex societal challenges like climate change, health, and AI in an era of misinformation. It explores effective strategies to foster trust, dialogue, and informed decision-making, aiming to strengthen science's role in society and policy.</p>				
NAME OF RESOURCE // PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Who may profit from this resource	Link
N&R Hubs generate ideas to strengthen science communication in times of crisis // COALESCE	Applicable on one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Trust	Anyone interested in science communication	https://coalesceproject.eu/2024/12/09/hubs-generate-ideas-to-strengthen-science-communication-in-times-of-crisis/
<p>This blog post recounts an activity with the COALESCE N&R Hubs, that focus on strengthening science communication to tackle disinformation and build trust during crises. Highlighting lessons from the COVID-19 pandemic, it addresses challenges like polarization, misinformation, and unclear expertise boundaries. Through the workshop led by the COALESCE project, the Hubs explored together the Crisis Navigator to tackle these issues at various crisis stages. Solutions proposed included media training for scientists, depolarizing debates, and fostering collaboration between scientists, policymakers, and governments. Includes an infographic by Edgar Sanjuán.</p>				

NAME OF RESOURCE // PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Co-designed virtual Competence Centre requirements specifications // COALESCE	Two-way approach	Science	Science communication actors	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12088890 appendix 2, page 67
The matchmaking tool under development by COALESCE, connecting science communication professionals, will help enhance collaboration, counter misinformation effectively, build trust in science, and promote accurate public understanding by fostering strategic, interdisciplinary partnerships between the different stakeholders.				
NAME OF RESOURCE // PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Podcast episode of SciComm Conversations: "Measuring trust in scientists" // COALESCE	Applicable on one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Trust	Academics, Anyone interested in science communication	https://coalesceproject.eu/2024/12/11/scicomm-conversations-s01e05/
This is a special episode of SciComm Conversations, with Dr Viktoria Cologna and Dr Niels Mede about their recent paper looking into trust in scientists . Together with colleagues from around the world, Viktoria and Niels studied the responses of nearly 72,000 participants in 68 countries on all inhabited continents.				
NAME OF RESOURCE // PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Who may profit from this resource	Link
SCIENCE MISINFORMATION IN SPAIN Report // IBERIFIER	Applicable on one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Misinformation and trust	Academics	https://www.fecyt.es/sites/default/files/users/user378/iberifier_report_scientific_misinformation_in_spain_publicacion.pdf
The objectives of this study are multiple, aiming to comprehensively understand the dynamics of misinformation on scientific topics in Spain. The study seeks to estimate the perceived credibility of misinformation and evaluate the level of trust individuals place in such messages. It further aims to assess people's ability to discern between true and false information, delving into the factors that influence this discernment. Additionally, the research explores personal strategies employed to detect misinformation and examines societal attitudes toward it. Another key objective is to estimate the likelihood of individuals spreading misinformation, alongside investigating the factors contributing to this behavior.				
NAME OF RESOURCE // PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Understanding and Addressing Misinformation About Science // National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine	Applicable on one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Misinformation	Academics and practitioners	https://doi.org/10.17226/27894
The National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine's 2024 report, "Understanding and Addressing Misinformation About Science," examines the proliferation of scientific misinformation in today's information ecosystem. It highlights how the ease of spreading false information complicates public understanding of science. The report emphasizes the need for effective strategies to counteract misinformation and enhance public comprehension of scientific topics.				

NAME OF RESOURCE // PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Who may profit from this resource	Link
The Debunking Handbook // <i>John Cook and Stephan Lewandowsky</i>	Applicable on one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Misinformation, climate change	Citizens, policymakers, journalists, and other scicomm practitioners	https://www.climatechangecommunication.org/all/handbook/the-debunking-handbook-2020/
<p>The 'Debunking Handbook 2020' summarizes the current state of the science of misinformation and its debunking. It was written by a team of 22 prominent scholars of misinformation and its debunking, and it represents the current consensus on the science of debunking for engaged citizens, policymakers, journalists, and other practitioners.</p>				
NAME OF RESOURCE // PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Wellcome Global Monitor // <i>Wellcome Foundation</i>	Applicable on one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Misinformation, trust, science, health, vaccines	Multilaterals, and researchers, general public	https://wellcome.org/reports/wellcome-global-monitor/2018 https://wellcome.org/reports/wellcome-global-monitor-covid-19/2020
<p>The 'Wellcome Global Monitor' reports from 2018 and 2020 focus on global public attitudes towards science, health, and vaccines. The 2018 report examines trust in scientists and health professionals, while the 2020 report explores changes in trust and vaccine acceptance during the COVID-19 pandemic. These insights help shape health policies.</p>				
NAME OF RESOURCE // PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Trust: The foundation of health systems // <i>WHO Team: European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies</i>	Applicable on one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Misinformation, disinformation, health	Policy makers	https://eurohealthobservatory.who.int/publications/i/trust-the-foundation-of-health-systems-study
<p>Recently published from the WHO health systems conference that happened in Tallinn in December 2023, based on the results of discussions with stakeholders, specifically ministers and senior officials. Focuses on threats to trust in health system. Check out Section 2.7 for mis-information / disinformation.</p>				
NAME OF RESOURCE // PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Tackling misinformation // <i>Ecsite</i>	Applicable on one-way, two-way and multi-way approaches	Misinformation, science engagement	Science communicators	https://www.ecsite.eu/activities-and-services/resources/tackling-misinformation
<p>The resource 'Tackling Misinformation' by Ecsite provides practical tools, evidence, and recommendations for science engagement professionals. Developed after a 2019 workshop in Copenhagen, it addresses misinformation challenges in public science communication through insights from researchers and practitioners. The guide emphasizes dialogue and effective practices for countering misinformation.</p>				

Reflecting on the listed resources, three main strategies to counter dis- and misinformation can be distinguished: Firstly, focussing on enhancing the dissemination of accurate information, such as leveraging the expertise of science journalists (e.g. in 'Informando de ciencia con ciencia' (Reporting Science Scientifically)) and supporting science communicators with tools like the Crisis Navigator for rapid response during crises (Reports "Crisis Navigator for Rapid Mobilisation of Science Communication" and "Hubs generate ideas to strengthen science communication in times of crisis").

Secondly, highlighting the broader societal impacts of disinformation, including during elections, and exploring policy measures at national and EU levels to address it (e.g. EDMO's reports 'Policies to tackle disinformation in EU member states'). These include non-legislative and legal approaches, though legal measures often spark concerns about freedom of expression.

Thirdly, strengthening public trust in science emerges as a key strategy, covered in resources that focus on findings from global studies (e.g. Podcast episode of SciComm Conversations: 'Measuring trust in scientists') and analyses of trust-building strategies in addressing complex societal challenges like climate change, health, and AI (e.g. 'Policy Brief on excellent scicomm for society at large through informal activities').

3.2 Digital and visual verification tools and media literacy programs

This section provides an overview of digital and visual tools which science communicators and the general audience can use to navigate mis- and disinformation on all platforms. We will look at essential tools like Botometer and Hoaxy, which are built on the emerging technologies of machine learning, blockchain and crowdsourcing to provide a content veracity scoring system⁷ that enables us to evaluate informations' trustworthiness, credibility and monitor misinformation patterns. These types of technologies are more relevant than ever, given the rapid pace and volume of information exchange can easily overwhelm traditional fact-checking and content-verification tools and methods. An analysis of these tools will show their effectiveness, the strategies they utilize, and their value as resources for professionals. We will also discuss the ethics of using these tools, particularly concerning privacy and misuse.

⁷ A content veracity scoring system evaluates the truthfulness, accuracy, and reliability of information by assigning scores based on factors like factual accuracy, source credibility, bias, and transparency. These scores help identify trustworthy content and reduce misinformation using tools like fact-checking, AI algorithms, and contextual analysis (Garcia-Lozano et al., 2020)

The RAND Corporation, a nonprofit organization dedicated to improving policy and decision-making through research and analysis, has recommended several tools to combat disinformation. This exploration highlights the current state of tools to support navigating dis- and misinformation, which are primarily technological. They consider the broader implications for media literacy, journalism, and the future of information integrity. To add to such existing recommendations, the Competence Centre will be curating effective tools to its platform during its further development.

Table 3. Resources and tools to help address misinformation

NAME OF TOOL// PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Free to use?	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Botometer // Trustees of Indiana University (Recommended by RAND)	Botometer is an online program that leverages machine learning to distinguish between bot and human X accounts. It assesses various profile features such as social network structure, activity patterns, language, and sentiment. The program provides an overall bot score ranging from 0 to 5 and additional scores indicating the likelihood of the account being a bot.	X, bots, misinformation	Yes	Science journalists, anyone with an interest in identifying bot activity	https://botometer.osome.iu.edu/#/faq Works with data collected on X before May 31, 2023
NAME OF TOOL// PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Free to use?	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Hoaxy (Observatory on Social Media) // Indiana University (Recommended by RAND)	Hoaxy (Observatory on Social Media) is a web-based tool that visualises the dissemination of online articles. Since 2016, it has tracked the sharing of links from low-credibility sources and fact-checking organisations. Hoaxy also calculates a bot score to gauge automation levels. The Observatory aims to study how information spreads online and its impact on public discourse.	Twitter, Bluesky, bots, misinformation	Yes	Science journalist, anyone with an interest in identifying bot activity	https://hoaxy.osome.iu.edu/
NAME OF TOOL// PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Free to use?	Who may profit from this resource	Link

TV News Fact Check // <i>TV news Archive</i> (Recommended by RAND)	TV News Fact Check is building an archive of various digital media, including political TV ads from 2016, accompanied by fact-checking from sources like PolitiFact and Factcheck.com.	fact-checking	Yes	Journalists, science communicators	https://archive.org/details/tv
NAME OF TOOL// PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Free to use?	Who may profit from this resource	Link
No Rumour Health // <i>No Rumour Health project</i> (<i>ScienceFlows, University of Valencia</i>)	No Rumour Health is a mobile application designed to help users easily detect and verify health misinformation. Its user-friendly interface is tailored for elderly individuals and adult learners with basic or low IT skills, making the app quick and easy to use. Anyone can download it for free on both Android and iOS.	Health, Misinformation	Yes	General Public, elderly population	https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=eu.dcnet.nrh
NAME OF TOOL// PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Free to use?	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Trustnet Browser Extension //MIT	Trustnet Browser Extension This is a free tool, designed to help users assess the credibility of online content. Since it's a browser extension, you can download and use it at no cost.	Flagging misinformation online	Yes	Anyone interested in science communication	https://chromewebstore.google.com/detail/trustnet/nphapibbiangbhamgmfgdeiiekddoejo?pli=1
NAME OF TOOL// PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Free to use?	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Combating misinformation online toolkit // WHO	The WHO's toolkit for combating misinformation online provides resources and strategies to address the spread of false health information. It includes collaborations with digital platforms, methods for promoting credible sources, algorithm adjustments to prioritize accurate content, and public awareness initiatives to improve digital	Misinformation, disinformation, health	Yes	Anyone interested in communication	https://www.who.int/teams/digital-health-and-innovation/digital-channels/combating-misinformation-online

	and health literacy. The goal is to ensure that trustworthy health information is accessible while minimizing the impact of misinformation.				
NAME OF TOOL// PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Free to use?	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Social media Fact Check Tools // Who	These tools are integrated into Social media's services, like Search and News, and are free. Users can access fact-checking information directly from search results without additional costs.	Misinformation, disinformation,	Yes	Anyone interested in communication	https://www.who.int/campaigns/connecting-the-world-to-combat-coronavirus/how-to-report-misinformation-online
NAME OF TOOL// PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Free to use?	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Fides // Who	Fides As part of WHO's initiatives, Fides identifies credible health information sources on social media.	Health	Yes	Anyone interested in health communication	https://www.who.int/teams/digital-health-and-innovation/digital-channels/fides
NAME OF TOOL// PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Free to use?	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Guide to stop the spread of hoaxes - in Spanish // FECYT	A visual resource aimed at providing practical advice to prevent the dissemination of misinformation. This guide is targeted at both the educational community and the general public. The guide is available in several formats: infographic, GIF and interactive.	Misinformation, Disinformation, Hoaxes	Yes	School teachers, general public	https://www.fecyt.es/es/educasinc/guia-para-frenar-la-difusion-de-bulos
NAME OF TOOL// PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Free to use?	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Infodemic infographic // Scientific infographics.	Infodemic—defined by WHO as an overabundance of information, both true & misleading, occurring during an epidemic. This infographic seeks to enhance public understanding of how infographics may influence behavior, exacerbate public	Misinformation in general. Factors that define an infodemic, and clues to prevent it.	Yes	All non specialised audiences	https://www.scientificinfographics.com/26-infodemic

NAME OF TOOL// PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Free to use?	Who may profit from this resource	Link
	health crises, & undermine trust in health authorities.				
Information... Is it true? // Scientific infographics.	This infographic emphasizes the importance of critically evaluating information in today's fast-paced digital world. It highlights how the ease of creating and distributing content can lead to the rapid spread of misinformation.	Misinformation	Yes	All non specialised audiences	https://www.scientificinfographics.com/23-information-is-it-true
NAME OF TOOL// PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Free to use?	Who may profit from this resource	Link
Full Fact // Full Fact	Full Fact is an independent fact-checking organization based in the UK. It investigates and counters misinformation by conducting systematic fact checks and campaigning for improved public debate. Their work includes addressing misinformation in areas like health, education, and politics, providing tools and training to enhance information quality, and advocating for better standards in online content and government communication.	Very broad – all areas of misinformation, not just in relation to science and technology	Yes	General public, journalists and others with a communication role.	https://fullfact.org/latest/
NAME OF TOOL// PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Free to use?	Who may profit from this resource	Link
CaSE Public Attitudes to R&D 2022-23 // The Campaign for Science and Engineering (CaSE) is the UK's leading independent advocate for science and engineering	The Campaign for Science and Engineering (CaSE) conducted a comprehensive study on public attitudes toward Research and Development (R&D) in the UK between 2022 and 2023. This research involved four nationally representative surveys, polling a total of 18,000 individuals, and	public attitudes	Yes	Academics, policy makers	https://www.sciencecampaign.org.uk/what-we-do/public-opinion/public-attitudes-to-r-d/

NAME OF TOOL// PROJECT or PROMOTER	Strategy / Approach	Topics Covered	Free to use?	Who may profit from this resource	Link
NewsGuard – news reliability ratings and 'misinformation fingerprints' <i>//NewsGuard</i>	NewsGuard – provides tools to counter misinformation such as reliability ratings of online content and 'misinformation fingerprints' – a catalogue of false (misinformation/disinformation) claims circulating online. NewsGuard also provides media literacy resources. The tools and resources are applicable to all topics relating to science, including health.	Misinformation, not only related to science matters	No	journalists, schools and universities, libraries, older people.	https://www.newsguardtech.com/

The reviewed tools, platforms, and initiatives overwhelmingly focus on empowering individual citizens to identify and combat dis- and misinformation. Many tools, such as Botometer, Hoaxy, and Trustnet Browser Extension, leverage advanced technologies like machine learning and social media data visualization to enable users, including journalists and the general public, to detect bot activity and misinformation patterns. Similarly, resources like No Rumour Health and Full Fact provide user-friendly interfaces tailored for non-specialized audiences, allowing individuals to assess the credibility of health and general information critically.

Although these tools provide valuable support for public education and awareness, their primary design appears reactive, targeting individuals to mitigate the consequences of misinformation rather than preventing its emergence at a systemic level. This citizen-focused approach may highlight a gap in structural and institutional interventions that could address the root causes of misinformation propagation. As such, these initiatives underline the critical role of digital and media literacy among the broader population while leaving room for more robust, top-down measures.

3.3 Integrating lessons from recent crisis communication

The DANA (“Isolated Depression at High Altitudes” acronym in Spanish) crisis on the 29th of October 2024 caused severe flooding in the Valencia region, in Spain, home to the University of Valencia, one of the COALESCE partners. This event resulted in over 220 deaths and highlighted critical challenges in crisis communication, particularly the role and

impact of misinformation. The scale of the crisis and the response to it created a significant awakening in the Spanish science and communication communities. To counter misinformation, at least 15 chronological timelines were published online by mainstream media, including newspapers, TV, and radio channels. Plus, notably, *El País*, the most widely read newspaper in the country, published a special [report on disinformation](#), by Javier Salas and highlighted on the cover on November 24th.

In line with this, a COALESCE workshop held in December 2024, as part of the [Euroscicomm2024 conference](#), brought together 30 experts and practitioners to identify actionable strategies to address misinformation in crisis situations involving science, in particular climate-related crisis, as the one resulting from the recent DANA. Hereby, we explore the key lessons learned from this event and how they can be integrated into the [Crisis Navigator](#) to enhance crisis preparedness and response efforts.

Misinformation Across Crisis Phases

The central focus of the workshop was the role of misinformation and its impact on public trust in scientific and governmental institutions. Participants, guided by COALESCE team members as moderators, reflected on communication failures, focused particularly on climate and emergency services, during the DANA crisis, grouping their observations into three distinct phases following the description of the [Crisis Navigator](#): pre-crisis, imminent-crisis, and post-crisis.

- In the **pre-crisis and imminent-crisis phases**, pre-existing misinformation, including conspiracy theories related to climate change and false narratives,

interferes with trust in scientific discourse (e.g. AEMET, Spain's meteorological agency) and political institutions. According to the findings of the TISP (Trust in Science and Science-Related Populism) project, which investigated the factors influencing trust in scientists and populist attitudes toward science on a global scale, Spain ranked 7th among the 67 countries assessed for public confidence in scientists. With an average score of 3.9 on a scale from 1 to 5, Spain emerges as one of the countries where the population exhibits an exceptionally high level of trust in the scientific community (Wong, 2024). However, the warning messages from the media and social networks just before the flood did not reach the public. In addition, messaging issues were further compounded by a lack of clear institutional information. Significantly, the failure to use an urgent tone when political figures communicated this risk to the public diminished the public's perception of the seriousness of the situation. Workshop participants noted that these challenges were aggravated by a lack of trained personnel in crisis and science communication and/or the absence of clear communication protocols or guides in key institutions. The **imminent-crisis phase** particularly revealed additional shortcomings in leadership and coordination among emergency services and public authorities. Social media, revealed as a critical tool for disseminating real-time updates by citizens.

- In the **post-crisis phase**, political discourse shifted toward assigning blame rather than providing solutions. Technological disruptions caused by power outages further limited access to credible and reliable information, leaving affected communities vulnerable to rumours and false reports. This dynamic exacerbated public dissatisfaction and fuelled misinformation aimed at discrediting scientists and public institutions, according to the prominent hoaxes collected by EDMO (2024). A lack of transparency and coordinated political action – driven by partisan priorities – further eroded trust in authorities.

Key Lessons and Recommendations for the Crisis Navigator

The workshop concluded with several key recommendations to address these challenges and improve future crisis communication. These lessons will inform updates to the [Crisis Navigator](#), ensuring it is equipped to counter misinformation effectively and strengthen trust between science, public authorities, and society.

- **Pre-Crisis Preparation:** Successful communication begins long before a crisis occurs. Clear and accessible protocols must be developed to identify misinformation risks and improve public understanding of evidence-based warnings. Drawing inspiration from successful models like the [PEVOLCA framework](#) used during the La Palma volcanic eruption, participants emphasized the need for

coordinated internal and external communication plans. This includes training teams to deliver concise, contextualized, and urgent messaging that resonates with diverse communities.

- **Effective Communication During Crisis:** The imminent-crisis phase requires prompt, coordinated communication to convey urgency and reduce misinformation. Public authorities must demonstrate leadership, ensuring their messages are clear, direct, and credible. Efforts to combat false information on social media must include real-time monitoring and partnerships with trusted media outlets.
- **Post-Crisis Evaluation and Learning:** Evaluating communication strategies after a crisis is essential to identify gaps and areas for improvement. Workshop participants recommended conducting participatory evaluations involving the public, to ensure future plans address the needs of affected communities.

Additionally, participants highlighted the importance of continuous training for communication professionals, emergency response teams, and political leaders to strengthen their ability to provide accurate and trustworthy information. Enhancing science-policy connections at municipal, regional, and national levels was also emphasized, as was the role of educators in fostering public understanding and building collective memory around crisis events.

By integrating these lessons into the [Crisis Navigator](#) in a future iteration, crisis management frameworks can better address misinformation challenges, strengthen public trust, and ensure more effective communication during future emergencies.

4. Recommendations and future actions

This final section draws together insights in this report to formulate future actions for COALESCE as well as recommendations that may involve individuals and organisations beyond the project. As such, it will inform the future activities of the COALESCE project as well as suggest recommended courses of action for others. Where possible, the activities of COALESCE and the European Competence Centre for Science Communication will seek to encourage and facilitate the implementation of any recommendations, such as through connections with existing networks and Communities of Practice.

4.1 Developing a sustainable misinformation toolkit

- **Support through synthesis, curation and promotion:** After mapping relevant existing resources and tools that address the science–society relationship to support navigating dis- and misinformation while maintaining trust in science, it can be concluded that the most effective and sustainable way to support existing efforts is through their synthesis, curation, and promotion.

While there are many resources that may support those who communicate science in efforts to address misinformation, identifying relevant resources can be challenging. Given that one of the main goals of the European Competence Centre for Science Communication is to guide science communicators to resources that encourage and enhance their work, it is recommended that the Competence Centre platform provides a searchable database (a misinformation toolkit) that curates existing resources and tools that will support those who communicate science. This may be, for example, information verification tools science communicators can use in their research, or existing guidelines on how to communicate in a way that engenders trust.

The central effort to achieve this is twofold: 1) To guide users of the Competence Centre platform to the resources that work best for them, their prior knowledge and needs must be considered in the navigation of the misinformation toolkit, and 2) As we aim for a sustainable strategy, the resources included and linked in the toolkit must be verified, maintained, and updated regularly. As resources are added, where these are specific to the communication of science, quality standards, principles

and criteria for science communication resources developed within COALESCE will be used to inform the selection process.

It is recommended that in the process of developing this searchable database, intended stakeholders/users of the Competence Centre platform will be matched to appropriate available resources (outlined in Tables 1, 2 and 3 of this report) so that each user is presented with resources and tools appropriate to them. These intended users are science communication professionals, journalists, citizens, policymakers, and those working in industry and academics.

- **Creating guidelines:** In keeping with the recommendations of previous SwafS-19 projects (such as ENJOI), short but simple, comprehensive guidelines should be written for science communication professionals and journalists. Such guidelines could draw together insights from previous SwafS-19 projects and elsewhere on effective approaches to science communication in the context of misinformation and maintaining public trust in science. Where feasible, specific guidelines relevant to different actors working in science communication, such as scientists, museum explainers and those working in multimedia communication will be developed in the context of the COALESCE project, for example, through development of a misinformation toolkit.

4.2 Strengthening networks and collaborative efforts to address the misinformation challenge

- **Connecting with EDMO:** connect with the national European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO), including its Hubs, and the [broader EDMO research community](#). Through these connections it will seek to encourage and contribute to practical projects related to science fact checking and science media literacy as well as research about science misinformation.
- **Collaborating with University Alliances:** work with University Alliances to encourage the integration of science communication activities within career development structures for researchers. Recognising and rewarding science communication activities by scientists would encourage increased communication of research insights, increasing the availability of trustworthy information on which citizens, policymakers and others can inform their decision making. The incentive structures should also encourage participatory approaches in research, including citizen science projects, given the role they play in fostering trust in science. Next to strengthening the incentives, mitigation strategies to counter impact of mis- and disinformation on researchers will be of relevance here, especially regarding how to

deal with attacks on individual researchers, institutions as well as with possible fear of threats among researchers who keep engaged in science communication.

- **Facilitating partnerships:** Establishing links between researchers, journalists, fact-checking organisations, and educational environments – whether for young people or older populations – helps to ensure that verified information about mis- and disinformation is disseminated effectively. This fosters independent fact-checking and creates well-suited formats for fast responses. The COALESCE project will work on this by development of a matchmaking tool between scientists and (science) communication professionals and by establishing a science communication academy.

4.3 Policy implications, research opportunities, and other recommendations

- **Development of science media literacy/wisdom initiatives:** There are already initiatives aimed at improving media literacy due to misinformation, a notable example being the work of the European Digital Media Observatory. However, given the individual and societal impact of misinformation about science, the iterative and self-correcting nature of scientific research and the online ecosystem of information about science, specific initiatives aimed at science media literacy, or science media wisdom, should be prioritised both within and outside of educational systems. Such initiatives may be supported by existing media literacy resources. These media literacy/wisdom initiatives should address the nature of the scientific process (and the self-correcting nature of science) as well as techniques to navigate the science media landscape, including on social media.
- **Science communication research on effective approaches to involve citizens in science in the context of misinformation:** While current resources aimed at informing science communication activities emphasise the importance of science-society relationship building, including citizen science, strategies concerning stakeholder and citizen engagement, dialogue and participation in the context of navigating misinformation in science remain underexplored.
- **Integration of effective approaches to addressing misinformation into the curricula of science communication courses at higher education institutions:** Science communication education at undergraduate and postgraduate level should integrate effective approaches to research for science communicators, including fact checking, as well as approaches to communication that engender trust.

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7. Project details

PROJECT NAME Coordinated Opportunities for Advanced Leadership and Engagement in Science Communication in Europe (COALESCE)

PARTNERS

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